

EXPERT MEETING

AUTONOMOUS WEAPON SYSTEMS

IMPLICATIONS OF INCREASING AUTONOMY IN THE CRITICAL FUNCTIONS OF WEAPONS

**VERSOIX, SWITZERLAND
15-16 MARCH 2016**

ICRC

ICRC

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SESSION 5: HUMAN CONTROL

Meaningful human control over individual attacks

Speaker's summary

Mr Richard Moyes, *Article 36*, UK

Introduction

“Meaningful human control over individual attacks” is a phrase coined by the non-governmental organization *Article 36* to express the core element that is challenged by the movement towards greater autonomy in weapon systems. It is a policy formulation that has been picked up and used in different ways: in publications by various individuals and organizations, in statements at review conferences of the States party to the UN Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW), in the open letter from artificial intelligence practitioners organized by the Future of Life Institute. As used by *Article 36*, it has always been presented as an approach for structuring a productive debate rather than as providing a conclusion to that debate.

Asserting a need for meaningful human control is based on the idea that concerns regarding growing autonomy are rooted in the human element that autonomy removes, and therefore describing this element is a necessary starting point if we are to evaluate whether current or future technologies challenge it. This is particularly important if we are to have a coherent policy conversation about diverse and often hypothetical future technologies. It is also a starting point for policy that is arguably more open to engagement by diverse parties who might have different expectations of the advantages that future developments in autonomous weapon systems might provide to them.

Considering the key elements necessary for human control to be meaningful does not preclude consideration of other more specific issues, but a structured analysis tends to find that those issues fall under the key elements of human control: for example, the need for “predictable” technology, the need for human judgement to be applied in the use of force, and the need for accountability, which we will look at later. Furthermore, without a normative requirement regarding human control, the legal framework itself is open to divergent and progressively broader interpretations that may render human application of the law meaningless.

Recognizing the need for human control in some form

At its most basic level, the requirement of meaningful human control develops from two premises:

1. that a machine applying violent force and operating without any human control whatsoever is broadly considered unacceptable;
2. that a human simply pressing a “fire” button in response to indications from a computer, without cognitive clarity or awareness, is not sufficient to be considered “human control” in a substantive sense.

On this basis, some human control is required, and it must be in some way substantial – we use the term “meaningful” to express that threshold. From both of these premises, questions relating to what is required for human control to be “meaningful” are open. Given that

openness, meaningful human control represents a space for discussion and negotiation. The word “meaningful” functions primarily as an indicator that the form or nature of human control should be assessed against a common standard and so necessarily requires further definition in policy discourse.

Critical responses to this policy formulation tend to fixate on the term “meaningful” because it is undefined or might be argued to be vague – responses that may also be motivated by State representatives’ anxiety over policy formulations not initiated by States. Such responses, however, miss the point. There are other words that could be used instead of “meaningful”, e.g. appropriate, effective, sufficient, or necessary. Any one of these terms leaves open the same crucial question: how will the international community delineate the main elements of human control needed to meet these criteria? Any one of these would also be vague until the necessary form of human control is further defined, giving the chosen adjective some further calibration.

The term “meaningful” can be argued to be preferable because it is broad, it is general, rather than context-specific (e.g. appropriate), it derives from an overarching principle rather than being outcome-driven (e.g. effective or sufficient), and it implies human meaning rather than something administrative, technical or bureaucratic.

That said, fixating on which adjective is most appropriate should not stand as a barrier to the next step required of the international community, which is to begin delineating the elements of human control that should be considered necessary in the use of force.

Situating human control in the legal framework

Article 36 has called on States, in the context of discussions on autonomous weapon systems in armed conflict, to recognize the need for “meaningful human control over individual attacks.” By its use of the term “attacks”, this formulation situates the issue of human control within the legal framework of international humanitarian law (IHL).

It is important to recognize that IHL is not the only legal framework relevant to autonomous weapon systems, nor are legal frameworks the only basis for assessing whether the further development of such technologies is appropriate or advisable. However, the relationship between human control, autonomous weapon systems and IHL are given particular focus here.

Human beings as addressees of the law

When discussing autonomous weapon systems, however complex, *Article 36* orients to these systems as “machines”. The discussion of this issue is prone to slippage towards treating these machines as “agents” and in particular as “legal agents”. It is common for diplomats and “experts” to refer to concerns about whether autonomous weapon systems will “be able to apply legal rules”, or “to follow the law”. Machines don’t apply legal rules. They may undertake functions that are in some ways analogous to the legal rules (for example, being programmed to apply force to certain heat patterns common to armoured fighting vehicles), but in doing so they are not “applying the law” – they are simply implementing a process that human commanders anticipate in their assessment of the legality of a planned attack. Prof. Marco Sassòli, in his presentation to the 2014 ICRC expert meeting on autonomous weapons, stated that “only human beings are addressees of international humanitarian law”.⁶

⁶ ICRC, *Autonomous Weapon Systems: Technical, Military, Legal and Humanitarian Aspects*, Report of an expert meeting held in Geneva, Switzerland on 26–28 March 2014, November 2014, p. 41.

Human judgement in relation to “attacks”: part of the structure of IHL

If human beings are the addressees of the law, whether collectively or individually, then there are certain boundaries of machine operation that the law implies in relation to humans. The term “attacks” in IHL designates a unit of military action, and it is to individual “attacks” that certain legal judgements must be applied. So attacks are part of the structure of the law.

For example, Article 57 of AP I provides rules on precautions to be taken in attack. Where it refers to “those who plan or decide upon an attack”, it is referring to humans. Therefore, it is humans who shall apply these legal rules, including verifying the objective, choosing the means and method of attack and refraining from or cancelling an attack in certain circumstances.

We know that an attack must be directed at a specific military objective; otherwise, it is indiscriminate (Article 51.4(a)). We also know that a military objective must be of a sort (nature, location, etc.) to offer military advantage at the time (Article 52.2), and that in the application of the legal rules, the concrete and direct military advantage must be assessed by humans who plan and decide upon an attack (Article 51.5(b) and Article 57.2(a)(i) and (iii)). Therefore, humans must make a legal determination about an attack on a specific military objective based on the circumstances at the time. There should also be a capacity to cancel or suspend an attack (Article 57.2(b)).

These rules imply that a machine cannot identify and attack a military objective without human legal judgement and control being applied in connection with an attack on that specific military objective at that time (control being necessary in some form to act on the legal judgement that is required). Arguing that this capacity can be programmed into the machine is an abrogation of human agency with respect to the law, breaching the “case-by-case” approach that forms the structure of these legal rules.

This line of argument is not dependent upon claims regarding the technical capacity of complex future autonomous weapon systems to do this or that, but is based on the law as a framework that applies to humans and that is structured to require human legal judgements at certain points.

However, this is not to argue that the law straightforwardly implies a very narrow constraint on what an autonomous weapon system might do under its existing terms. Nor is it suggesting that existing law alone represents a sufficient basis for managing such weapon systems. It is simply to point out that the existing legal structure (human judgement being required with regard to “attacks”) implies certain boundaries to independent machine operation, and that this is separate from arguments about how a machine might perform in relation to the implementation of individual legal rules (for example, the rule of proportionality).

Conceptualizing “an attack”

While an assumption of human legal judgement in relation to individual attacks is seen in the structure of the law, it is also recognized that “an attack” is not necessarily a single application of kinetic force to a single target object. In practice, an attack may involve multiple kinetic events against multiple specific target objects. However, there have to be some spatial, temporal or conceptual boundaries to an attack if the law is to function. This is linked to the different layers at which military action is often conceptualized – from the local tactical level, through the operational level, to the broad strategic level. If “attacks” were not conceptualized and subject to legal judgement at the tactical level, but only at the broad strategic level, then a large operation may be determined to be permissible (on the basis of broad anticipated outcomes) while containing multiple individual actions that would in

themselves be violations of the law. Clearly, for the law to function meaningfully, there need to be legal judgements and accountability for actions at the most local level.

Recognition that human legal engagement must occur with each attack means that a machine cannot proceed from one attack to another without such human legal judgement being applied in each case, and without the capacity for the results of that legal judgment to be acted upon in a timely manner – i.e. through some form of control system. Given that, under the law, an attack is carried out against a specific military objective that has been subject to human assessment in the circumstances prevailing at the time, it follows that a machine cannot set its own military objective without human authorization based on a human legal judgement.

Preventing an expansion of the concept of “an attack”

Our starting point in this discussion was concern that greater autonomy in weapon systems may result in human control not being meaningful. Based on the above analysis regarding the relationship of autonomy to the legal framework, we can see that this concern is linked to a risk that autonomy in certain critical functions of weapon systems might produce an expansion of the concept of “an attack” away from the granularity of the tactical level towards the operational and strategic levels. That is to say, there is a risk of autonomous weapon systems being used in “attacks” which, in their overly broad spatial, temporal or conceptual boundaries, go significantly beyond the units of military action over which specific legal judgement would currently be expected to be applied.

A more specific legal assessment – in other words, a legal assessment of specific events that are expected to occur over a shorter period of time and within a narrower area – makes it possible more accurately to assess specific risks to the civilian population and therefore to enhance protection of civilians. Furthermore, allowing greater autonomy to facilitate progressively broader interpretations of what constitutes an attack would have a corrosive effect on the legal framework as a whole. This raises a key objection to assertions that national weapon review processes would be a sufficient response to the concerns posed by autonomous weapons. If the very tests that are applied to determine the permissibility of a weapon system are being undermined by the development of that weapon system itself, how can the review process based solely on those tests remain meaningful?

By asserting the need for meaningful human control over attacks in the context of autonomous weapon systems, States would be affirming a principle intended to protect the structure of the law as a framework for the application of wider moral principles. Moving the debate onward to delineate the elements needed for human control to be meaningful would foster a normative understanding that should pull towards greater specificity in legal assessment, rather than greater generalization.

Key elements of human control

Thus, as outlined in the previous section, a meaningful form of human control is necessary both to allow for legal application and to protect the structure of the law from progressive erosion. In that context, the section below lays out key elements through which human control can be understood to be applied in the use of weapon systems. These elements are not simply about technological characteristics; they recognize that human control is necessarily part of a wider system that allows a specific technology to be controlled in a specific context of use.

Predictable, reliable and transparent technology

Starting with technology itself, human control is facilitated where the technology is:

- predictable (it can be expected to respond in certain ways);
- reliable (it is not prone to failure, and is designed to fail without causing outcomes that should be avoided); and
- transparent (practical users can understand how it works).

However the technology is to be used, it can be designed and manufactured with certain characteristics that have a bearing upon the subsequent capacity for human control. A technology that is by design unpredictable, unreliable and non-transparent is necessarily more difficult for a human to control in a given situation of use.

Providing accurate information for the user on the outcome sought, the technology and the context of use

Human control in the use of a given technology is thus based on those who plan and decide upon an attack having certain information. Control in the use of a weapon system can be understood as a mechanism for achieving the commander's intent. So information on the objective sought – and among other things, on the unintended consequences that a commander wishes to avoid – is an important starting point. This information is necessary for a human commander to assess the validity of a specific military objective at the time of an attack and to evaluate a proposed attack in the context of the legal rules.

Such assessments also require an understanding of the technology. For example, we need to know what types of object a weapon system will identify as a target object – i.e. target profiles – whether these are the commander's intended targets or not. We need to know how kinetic force will be applied. It makes a difference whether the force consists of a heavy explosive weapon with a large blast and fragmentation radius, or whether force will be applied quite narrowly, e.g. through an explosively formed projectile with no fragmentation effects.

Predictability is an important concept, in that it provides a link between the commander's intent and the likelihood of outcomes matching that intent. Predictability is partly a characteristic of the technology, but more fundamentally it is a characteristic of the interaction between that technology and the specific environment within which it will operate. As a result, information that enhances our understanding of the context of use, including the presence of civilians and civilian objects, for example, is very significant.

Of course we may not achieve complete predictability. Already, in the use of weapons, commanders accept degrees of uncertainty about the actual effects that will occur, and we know that there may be limitations on the information available about the context. However, our ability to understand the context is directly linked to both the size of the area within which the technology will operate, and the duration of its operation. For any given environment, it follows logically that a larger area and longer duration of independent operation by a technology result in reduced predictability and thus reduced human control.

It is recognized that different environments have different general characteristics, with the land, air and sea presenting different levels of complexity. This may mean that a large area of operation at sea may still facilitate better contextual understanding than a smaller area on land. However, given environments of equal complexity, a larger area and longer time of operation still mean reduced control. In relation to the duration of an attack, this might be because certain people or objects enter or leave an area over time in a way that could not be anticipated, or it might be because the commander's intent has changed from the time when the attack was initiated.

From an understanding of the technology and the context in which it will operate, a

commander should be able to assess likely outcomes, including the risk of civilian harm, which is the basis for the legal assessment. It is important to note that information on these different elements may be the product of wider human and technological systems, but at some point the understanding of these three elements must coalesce to a degree where an informed judgement can be made.

Timely human judgement and action, and the potential for timely intervention

Based on the information on the outcome sought, the technology and the context, we need humans to apply their judgement, as implied by the legal analysis above, and to choose to activate the technology. This point of human engagement ties together the systems of information upon which judgements are made, but also provides a primary reference point for the framework of accountability within which these actions are taking place. Of course, responsibility for negative outcomes may turn out to result from problems elsewhere in the system (e.g. malfunctioning technology or inaccurate information on the context of use), but human judgement and action are likely to be the starting point from which any negative outcomes are investigated.

The timeliness of this process is also significant because the accuracy and relevance of the information upon which it is based – about the context, for example – also degrade over time. For a system that may operate over a longer period, a clear capacity for timely intervention (e.g. to stop the independent operation of a system) will be necessary if it is not to operate outside the framework of necessary human control.

A framework of accountability

Finally, this broad system requires structures of accountability. Such structures should encompass not just the commander responsible for a specific attack, but also the wider system which produces and maintains the technology and which produces information on the outcomes being sought and the context of use.

Conclusion on the key elements of human control

All of these areas cumulatively contribute to the extent of human control that is being applied in a specific context of use. In all of these areas, there are tests of sufficiency that would need to be met in order for the extent of human control itself to be assessed as sufficient. Where some have asserted that the existing legal framework provides the answers needed for evaluating autonomous weapon systems, these tests suggest that this is not straightforwardly the case.

It is not clear, for example, what level of information about the context in which a weapon will be used is considered sufficient to provide a basis for an informed legal judgement. If a weapon system were to apply force to the individual vehicles of a group of fighting vehicles, this might be considered reasonable if the group were known to be in a bounded geographical area of which a commander had knowledge. However, if the area in which that group of vehicles was situated was spread over a wider area, about which the commander necessarily had a lesser and lesser understanding, at what point does that understanding become so diluted as to make a legal assessment unreasonable? In legal terms, this is a question about what can reasonably be considered a specific military objective and what can reasonably be considered an attack. The law alone does not provide an answer to these questions that resolves the uncertainty here, yet such questions are fundamental to avoiding the erosion of the legal framework that can be envisaged should States choose to develop autonomous weapon systems.

While consideration of the key elements of human control does not immediately provide the

answers to such questions either, it would at least allow States to recognize that these questions are fundamental, and it provides a framework within which certain normative understandings should start to be articulated, which is vital to an effective response to the challenge posed by autonomous weapon systems.

Working definitions: facilitating discussion within the framework of the CCW

The most direct way to establish such a discussion within the framework of the CCW is to adopt an approach to working definitions that is based on the recognition that certain forms of human control over the use of force are required, and that systems operating outside such control should not be considered acceptable. That would most straightforwardly be facilitated by adopting a working definition of “lethal autonomous weapon systems” that is based on their being “weapon systems operating with elements of autonomy and without the necessary forms of human control”. In such an approach, the concept of weapon systems operating with elements of autonomy then refers to a broad category of systems within which a certain subset (either by design or by their manner of use) is considered unacceptable. Such an approach then paves the way for delineation of the key elements of human control as a primary focus of work in order to understand where the boundaries of permissibility should lie.